

Studies in Quinones. Part IV. Preparation of 5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone and its Derivatives

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5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone and its derivatives have been prepared and their behaviour with other reagents has been studied.

In connection with a project underway in this laboratory on benzoquinones and their peculiarities, the title compound was required. For this purpose, 4-chloro-6-nitro-2-methylanisole, obtained by methylation of 4-chloro-6-nitro-2-methylphenol¹, was reduced and the product acetylated. The nitration of the acetyl derivative, followed by hydrolysis of the product, furnished 4-chloro-6-amino-3-nitro-2-methylanisole. This was reduced and the product then oxidised by ferric chloride to yield 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone.

Reduction of the quinone by sulphurous acid furnished the expected hydroquinone. Acetylation of the latter, however, yielded the triacetyl derivative², the demethylation taking place during the process. The chloromethoxy-quinone on keeping with 5 *N*-HCl for some time provided 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone³.

When 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone was hydrogenated over palladised calcium carbonate, 3-methyl-2-methoxyhydroquinone³ was obtained, oxidation of which furnished the corresponding quinone⁴. The reaction of 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone with dry sodium methoxide in benzene furnished 2,5-dimethoxy-3-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Hydroxy-5 chlorobenzaldehyde, prepared from *p*-chlorophenol by heating with hexamine and glyceroboric acid in anhydrous glycerine and subsequent acidification, was subjected to Clemmensen's reduction. Nitration of the derived chlorocresol furnished 4-chloro-6-nitro-2-methylphenol, m.p. 107° (lit.¹ m.p. 107°), identical with the product afforded by chlorination of 6-nitro-2-methylphenol in glacial acetic acid.

1. Zincke, *Annalen*, 1918, 417, 222.
2. Zincke and Preiss, *ibid.*, 1918, 417, 217.
3. Majima and Okazaki, *Ber.*, 1916, 49, 1490.
4. Hanger *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 496.
5. Teuber and Haasselbach, *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, 92, 674.

4-Chloro-6-nitro-2-methylanisole.—A mixture of 4-chloro-6-nitro-2-methylphenol (3 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g.), and dimethyl sulphate (4.2 g.) in dry acetone (30 ml) was refluxed for 5 hr. and then filtered. The potassium salts were washed with hot acetone and the combined acetone filtrates distilled. The residue was stirred with a 20% solution of NaOH (30 ml) and then extracted with ether. On removing the ether from the dried extract, the residue was crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) to furnish the anisole in colorless needles (3 g.), m.p. 49°. (Found: N, 6.85; Cl, 17.42. $C_8H_8O_3NCl$ requires N, 6.95; Cl, 17.59%).

4-Chloro-6-amino-2-methylanisole.—Iron powder (7 g.) was gradually added to a suspension of the aforesaid nitroanisole (8 g.) in a solution of HCl (conc., 1.5 ml) in water (25 ml), maintaining the temperature at 60°. The mixture was then refluxed for 3 hr., cooled, neutralised with sodium carbonate, and steam-distilled. The aminoanisole, isolated from the distillate by ether in the usual way, was obtained as a light yellow oil (4.8 g.) on fractional distillation: b.p. 142°/20 mm. (Found: N, 7.86; Cl, 20.35. $C_8H_{10}ONCl$ requires N, 8.16; Cl, 20.66%).

Its acetyl derivative was crystallised from dilute acetic acid (1:1) in colorless needles, m.p. 105°. (Found: N, 6.75; Cl, 16.35. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2NCl$ requires N, 6.56; Cl, 16.59%).

4-Chloro-6-amino-3-nitro-2-methylanisole.—To a cooled solution of the above mentioned acetyl derivative (1.3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) and H_2SO_4 (d 1.82, 5 ml) was gradually added a mixture of HNO_3 (d 1.42, 1 ml) and H_2SO_4 (d 1.82, 0.5 ml), maintaining the temperature below 10°. After keeping the mixture at 10° for an hour, it was allowed to stay for another hour at the room temperature (15°) with constant stirring. The nitroacetanilide separating on pouring the mixture in ice-cold water was crystallised from aqueous ethanol (1:1) in light yellow crystals (1 g.), m.p. 161°. (Found: N, 10.65; Cl, 13.42. $C_{10}H_{11}O_4N_2Cl$ requires N, 10.83; Cl, 13.71%).

On refluxing the nitroacetanilide (2 g.) with a solution of HCl (conc., 10 ml) in ethanol (10 ml) and cooling, the hydrochloride of 4-chloro-6-amino-3-nitro-2-methylanisole separated as faint yellow plates (1 g.), m.p. 180-85°. When the filtrate was concentrated, more of the hydrochloride (0.3 g.) was obtained. (Found: N, 10.77; Cl, 27.82. $C_8H_9O_3N_2Cl$, HCl requires N, 11.07; Cl, 28.02%).

The hydrochloride (2 g.) was treated with 5% KOH (10 ml) to furnish a yellow solid (1.5 g.). It was crystallised from hot water in pale yellow needles, m.p. 68°. (Found: N, 12.87; Cl, 16.21. $C_8H_9O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 12.93; Cl, 16.36%).

5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone.—A mixture of 4-chloro-6-amino-2-methyl-3-nitroanisole (2 g.), iron powder (2 g.) and 10% aqueous acetic acid (20 ml) was heated on a boiling water bath for an hour and filtered. The filtrate was neutralised with sodium carbonate and extracted with ether (3 × 50 ml). The residue obtained on removing the ether was added to ferric chloride (8 g.), dissolved in water (20 ml). The mixture was steam-distilled immediately. The quinone separating as an orange solid in the distillate was filtered and the filtrate extracted with ether to collect more of the quinone. The red solid was crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) in light red needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 71°. (Found: C, 51.75; H, 3.95; Cl, 19.21; OMe, 16.41. $C_8H_7O_3Cl$ requires C, 51.49; H, 3.78; Cl, 19.00; OMe, 16.63%).

5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxyhydroquinone.—Sulphur dioxide was bubbled in a solution of the above quinone (0.5 g.) in aqueous ethanol (5 ml, 5:3) till the yellow colour was discharged. Extraction of the solution with ether and removal of the ether from the dried extract under reduced pressure yielded white needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 97-101°. It was crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) in colorless needles, m.p. 105°. (Found: C, 50.74; H, 4.66; Cl 18.65; OMe, 16.11. $C_8H_9O_3Cl$ requires C, 50.94; H, 4.81; Cl, 18.80; OMe, 16.45%).

Acetylation in the usual way (acetic anhydride and sodium acetate) furnished a triacetyl derivative which was crystallised from aqueous methanol in colorless needles, m.p. 97° (lit.² m.p. 97°). (Found: C, 51.73; H, 4.19; Cl, 11.89. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{13}O_6Cl$: C, 51.92; H, 4.36; Cl, 11.79%).

5-Chloro-2-hydroxy-3-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone.—A fine dispersion of 5-chloro-2-methoxy-3-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone (1 g.) in 5*N*-HCl (20 ml) was allowed to stay overnight. On filtration, the residue was chromatographed on silica from petroleum (b.p. 60-80°). The first few fractions afforded 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone; m.p. and mixed m.p. 71°. Further elution with the petroleum yielded 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-3-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone in red needles, m.p. 61° (lit.² m.p. 60°). (Found: C, 48.52; H, 2.78; Cl, 20.24. Calc. for $C_7H_5O_3Cl$: C, 48.72; H, 2.92; Cl, 20.55%).

3-Methyl-2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone.—A solution of 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone (1.8 g.) in methanol was shaken under hydrogen at the room temperature (17°) and atmospheric pressure in presence of palladised calcium carbonate catalyst (from 0.2 g. calcium carbonate and 5 ml of 2% palladium chloride). After the hydrogen uptake had ceased, the residue from the filtered solution was crystallised from light petroleum to yield 3-methyl-2-methoxyhydroquinone in colorless needles, m.p. 120° (lit.³ m.p. 117-18°). (Found: C, 62.36; H, 6.32; OMe, 19.91. Calc. for $C_8H_{10}O_3$: C, 62.32; H, 6.54; OMe, 20.13%).

A solution of the hydroquinone (5 g.) in acetone (25 ml) was added slowly with stirring to a solution of Fremy's salt (25 g.) and sodium acetate (1.6 g.) in water (250 ml). The mixture was stirred for 1 hr. at the room temperature and then extracted with ether. The product was isolated from ether in the usual way and then distilled (b.p. 110°/15 mm; lit.⁴ b.p. 104°/12 mm.) to furnish a yellow oil which solidified at about 20-22° (lit.⁴ m.p. 19-20°). (Found: C, 63.39; H, 5.11; OMe, 20.12. Calc. for $C_8H_8O_3$: C, 63.15; H, 5.30; OMe, 20.39%).

2,5-Dihydroxy-3-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone.—A solution of *N*-NaOH (90 ml) was added during 30 min. to a warm (60°) solution of 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone (1.3 g.) in methanol (100 ml) and the solution was then left for 30 min. Acidification with 2*N*-HCl of the cooled solution provided an orange-brown solid which was collected, dried, and extracted with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°). The petroleum solution was filtered, concentrated to 20 ml, and then cooled when an orange solid was obtained (150 mg.) which at 125°/0.1 mm yielded a semicrystalline, reddish brown sublimate. The sublimate was crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) to furnish 2,5-dihydroxy-3-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone as orange leaflets (60 mg.), m.p. 177° (lit.⁶ m.p. 157°). (Found: C, 54.42; H, 3.59. Calc. for $C_7H_6O_4$: C, 54.55; H, 3.92%).

Reductive acetylation yielded 2,3,5,6-tetra-acetoxytoluene which crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 198° (lit⁶. m.p. 198°). (Found: C, 55.32; H, 4.85. Calc. for C₁₃H₁₆O₈: C, 55.55; H, 4.97%).

2,5-Dimethoxy-3-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone.—(i). A solution of 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone (1.8 g.) in anhydrous ether (100 ml) was shaken with dry sodium methylate (0.6 g.) in an atmosphere of nitrogen for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. On filtration, the ethereal solution was successively washed with water, aqueous HCl, and water till the washings were neutral to litmus. On removing ether from the dried ether extract, the residue was chromatographed on silica from petroleum (b.p. 60-80°). The first few fractions provided the dimethoxyquinone which was crystallised from methanol in yellow needles (80 mg.), m.p. 122° (lit⁵. m.p. 120°). (Found: C, 59.10; H, 5.32; OMe, 33.81. Calc. for C₉H₁₀O₄: C, 59.33; H, 5.53; OMe, 34.07%).

(ii). 2,5-Dihydroxy-3-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone (0.30 g.) in dimethylformamide (9 ml) was shaken for 73 hr. with silver oxide (0.9 g.) and methyl iodide (6 ml). The residue after filtration was washed with small quantities of (1:1) ether-dimethylformamide. The washings were combined with the filtrate which was then diluted with ether (60 ml) and extracted with aqueous potassium cyanide to remove silver salts. After being washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄), the ethereal solution was evaporated to a residue which was crystallised from methanol to furnish a quinone (0.18 g.), identical to that described under (i), m.p. and mixed m.p. 122°.

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